

The Role of State in Educational Training for the Ethical Use of social media: A Study in the Light of the Holy Qur'an, Hadith and the Prophetic Seerah

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ABSTRACT

In the contemporary world, social media has become a powerful medium that not only facilitates communication but also influences the intellectual and moral development of the youth. Its constructive use, however, requires guidance rooted in the Seerah of the ﷺ, who emphasized truth, honesty and goodwill as the foundations of communication. The state holds a vital responsibility to design educational curricula and training programs that incorporate media literacy, ethical awareness and religious values. Such initiatives can inspire students to utilize digital platforms positively for learning, research, preaching and social reform, rather than limiting them to mere entertainment. Alongside education, effective legislation and regulatory frameworks are essential to counter falsehood, rumors, hate speech and immorality on social media. Policies must ensure that the principles of justice, truth and responsibility are observed in all forms of digital interaction. From the perspective of the Prophetic Seerah ﷺ, the role of the state extends beyond legal measures to a holistic framework integrating intellectual, ethical and spiritual values. This approach can help nurture balanced, responsible and morally aware citizens, ultimately promoting social harmony and collective progress. Thus, when used constructively under the guidance of Qur'an, Hadith and the Seerah of the ﷺ, social media transforms into a tool for education, moral refinement and societal well-being.

Keywords: social media, State Responsibility, Seerah of the ﷺ, Media Literacy, Ethical Awareness, Social Harmony

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In the modern age, social media has become an inseparable aspect of daily human life. It has transformed the ways of communication and the exchange of information while also creating new opportunities for education, research, intellectual dialogue and social connections. At the same time, its careless use has led to serious challenges such as moral decline, confusion of thought, the spread of false news and social disintegration. In this situation, the state carries an enhanced responsibility to design a comprehensive and effective framework for the moral and intellectual training of the younger generation.

Islamic teachings provide clear ethical and spiritual guidelines regarding communication and the sharing of knowledge. The Seerah of the ﷺ offers us illuminating examples of how truthfulness, honesty, goodwill and wisdom were prioritized in conveying messages. His noble life demonstrates that all social interactions, whether spoken or written, must be governed by moral values. These timeless principles remain equally relevant for guiding the constructive and positive use of social media in the present era.

Principles of Communication in the Seerah of the ﷺ

In Islam, the principles of communication provide guidance not only for an individual's personal life but also for social relations and state responsibilities. The practical life of the Holy Prophet ﷺ is the best example of these principles, which serve as a beacon for the effective and ethical use of modern means of communication, especially social media.

Truthfulness and Trustworthiness

The most fundamental principle in communication is truthfulness and trustworthiness. The Holy Prophet ﷺ was granted the titles Al-Sadiq and Al-Amin even before the declaration of Prophethood.¹ This is practical evidence that the effectiveness of any message depends on its truth and honesty. In today's era, when social media is filled with false news and rumors, this principle becomes even more significant for teaching the young generation responsible communication.

Wisdom and Gentleness

Another important aspect of effective communication is wisdom and gentleness. The Holy Qur'an states:

"ادْعُ إِلَى سَبِيلِ رَبِّكَ بِالْحُكْمَةِ وَالْمَوْعِظَةِ الْحَسَنَةِ وَجَادِلْهُمْ بِالَّتِي هِيَ أَحْسَنُ إِنَّ رَبَّكَ هُوَ
أَعْلَمُ بِمَن ضَلَّ عَنْ سَبِيلِهِ وَهُوَ أَعْلَمُ بِالْمُهْتَدِينَ ﴿١٢٥﴾"

Translation: "Invite to the way of your Lord with wisdom and good instruction and argue with them in a way that is best. Indeed, your Lord is most knowing of who has strayed from His way and He is most knowing of who is [rightly] guided."

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The Holy Prophet ﷺ always preferred to speak according to the occasion, the context and the state of the addressee. It is narrated from Aisha (RA) that the speech of the ﷺ was always clear, well-ordered and understandable, such that every listener comprehended it immediately.³ This indicates that the ﷺ adjusted his words and style of speech according to the mental capacity, circumstances and situation of the audience, so that the message could reach in a more effective and meaningful way. The Qur'an confirms this principle, where believers are instructed to call people towards the way of Allah with wisdom and good counsel and to adopt a gentle and effective style in dialogue so that the message may be better understood.⁴

Both these sources clearly reflect that it is necessary to consider the occasion, situation and state of the audience in invitation and teaching, as the ﷺ always did. Effective communication is not merely about transmitting information but is the art of influencing hearts deeply. Ibn al-Qayyim states: "To give everything its due right, not to exceed its limit, to do it at its proper time, neither with haste nor with delay. Wisdom is that a person knows the reality and acts upon it and that both speech and action are correct."⁵

From this principle, it is understood that every act or statement, if performed with wisdom, will be balanced, proportionate and appropriate, which partly supports your concept (to adorn communication with wisdom). In the light of the principle of wisdom, communication should be designed to serve social welfare, reform of society and sincerity.

Sincerity and Reform

The fundamental objective of Islamic communication is sincerity and reform. The Holy Prophet ﷺ said:

"الدِّينُ النَّصِيحَةُ"⁶

Translation: "Al-Din is a name of sincerity and well-wishing."

From this, we learn that every communication should carry the element of benefit and reform, while avoiding the promotion of social hatred or prejudice. Communication is not limited to information only but should also be used for social welfare and moral training.

Holy Prophet ﷺ said:

"مَنْ دَلَّ عَلَى خَيْرٍ فَلَهُ مِثْلُ أَجْرِ فَاعِلِهِ"⁷

Translation: "One who guides to something good has a reward similar to that of its doer."

This Hadith indicates that whoever guides others to a good deed will receive a reward equal to that of the one who performs it. This principle is fully applicable in today's digital age as well. If social or digital media is used to promote goodness, knowledge and guidance, it can

become a continuous charity for a person. However, if these means are used to spread falsehood, hatred, or discord, the same action becomes a source of social corruption and moral decline.

If the media utilizes all its means and methods of communication for positive and constructive purposes, it can become an effective tool for promoting peace, tolerance and mutual respect within societies. The media has the power to replace hatred, prejudice and violence with dialogue, understanding and cooperation. When media policies and broadcasts are aimed at spreading truth, justice and the welfare of humanity, they can play a vital role in establishing lasting peace at the global level. In this way, the media not only serves as a source of information but also becomes a messenger of peace and harmony, contributing to the betterment of humankind.⁸

Moderation and Responsibility

Islamic teachings explain that in the early stages of religiosity, a person develops a particular enthusiasm and zeal for worship, but this state does not remain permanent. With time, it takes the form of calmness, moderation and balance. The real criterion is that if a servant maintains this moderation and balance and continues to fulfill his religious duties properly, he is considered worthy of Allah's mercy and acceptance. However, if a person adopts such extremism and severity in worship that it becomes an extraordinary display or a cause of public criticism, then its religious status becomes doubtful and such behavior cannot be expected to bring good.⁹

This principle must also be adopted in laws and policy-making. Moderation is not limited to material affairs but is equally required in moral behavior, communication, social relations and public decisions. In today's era, especially in the use of social media and other modern means of communication, this principle encourages youth and citizens to adopt responsible behavior.

According to Islamic teachings, the state is entrusted with the moral responsibility of guiding the public and ensuring their welfare. The Qur'an says:

"إِنَّ اللَّهَ يَأْمُرُكُمْ أَنْ تُؤَدُّوا الْأَمَانَاتِ إِلَىٰ أَهْلِهَا وَإِذَا حَكَمْتُمْ بَيْنَ النَّاسِ أَنْ تَحْكُمُوا بِالْعَدْلِ" ١٠

Translation: "Indeed, Allah commands you to render trusts to whom they are due and when you judge between people to judge with justice."

This verse highlights the foremost responsibility of the state, which is not merely administrative but also a moral and religious duty.

State Responsibility and Practical Measures Regarding social media

In the modern era, the use of social media has deeply influenced the thinking, behavior and social relations of the younger generation. In this context, it is the moral, legal and educational responsibility of the state to promote the positive use of social media, reduce its negative impacts and maintain social harmony. In today's world, thanks to various web search

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engines, access to global information has become a matter of just a few moments. Information on any topic can instantly appear on a computer or mobile screen. Similarly, through email, videos, audio files, images and written (composed) documents can be sent to any part of the world within seconds. This fast-paced technology has made communication and the exchange of information remarkably easy and efficient.¹¹

Curriculum and Media Literacy

Education and training are the fundamental pillars of state responsibility. The Qur'an states:

"هُوَ الَّذِي بَعَثَ فِي الْأُمِّيِّينَ رَسُولًا مِّنْهُمْ يَتْلُو عَلَيْهِمْ آيَاتِهِ وَيُزَكِّيهِمْ وَيُعَلِّمُهُمُ الْكِتَابَ وَالْحِكْمَةَ" ١٢

Translation: "It is He who has sent among the unlettered a Messenger from themselves reciting to them His verses and purifying them and teaching them the Book and wisdom."

This verse makes it clear that education and purification are among the fundamental objectives of Prophethood. In the modern age, the state should include media literacy, moral training, the teachings of the Seerah of the ﷺ and principles of verifying news in the curriculum. Teacher training and workshops are essential to create awareness among youth about the positive use of social media. These measures help protect young people from false news, obscenity and hate speech.

Legal Framework and Policy

The legal responsibility of the state is just as important as its educational and moral responsibility. The Qur'an states:

"وَلْتَكُنْ مِنْكُمْ أُمَّةٌ يَدْعُونَ إِلَى الْخَيْرِ وَيَأْمُرُونَ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَيَنْهَوْنَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ وَأُولَئِكَ هُمُ الْمُفْلِحُونَ ﴿١٠٣﴾" ١٣

Translation: "And let there be [arising] from you a nation inviting to [all that is] good, enjoying what is right and forbidding what is wrong and those will be the successful."

In the light of this verse, the state should take the following measures:

1. Restrictions on false news and rumors: Effective laws should be enforced against false and misleading content on social media platforms and news channels.
2. Control of hate speech and prejudice: Prevent the spread of hate content on social media against race, religion, or social groups.
3. Encouragement of constructive and positive content: Government, educational institutions and media should promote positive and ethical content.

4. Digital accountability and monitoring: Ensure transparency and responsibility in online communication and digital platforms.

Public Awareness and Training

Along with legal and educational measures, the awakening of public awareness is also essential. The Qur'an states:

"وَتَعَاوَنُوا عَلَى الْبِرِّ وَالتَّقْوَىٰ ۖ وَلَا تَعَاوَنُوا عَلَى الْإِثْمِ وَالْعُدْوَانِ" - ١٤

Translation: And cooperate in righteousness and piety, but do not cooperate in sin and aggression."

The Messenger ﷺ said:

"مَنْ كَانَ يُؤْمِنُ بِاللَّهِ وَالْيَوْمِ الْآخِرِ فَلْيَقُلْ خَيْرًا أَوْ لِيَصْمُتْ" - ١٥

Translation: "Anybody who believes in Allah and the Last Day should talk what is good or keep quiet."

The state should, through public awareness programs, workshops, seminars and social media campaigns, provide training to youth and citizens for positive, responsible and ethical use of social media.

Technical Measures and Monitoring

Due to the increasing use of social media, problems such as fake news, hateful content and cybercrimes have emerged, for which technical measures and monitoring are inevitable. Platforms, through advanced algorithms, artificial intelligence and security protocols, filter harmful content and protect users' data, while under monitoring, real-time tracking, government supervision and complaint systems from users are utilized. Although balancing between freedom of expression and censorship is a challenge, these measures can prove effective in making social media safe and constructive.

Social Media and Contemporary Challenges

In the modern era, electronic media is regarded as the fastest and most effective means of communication among all media sources. Through it, any news can reach every corner of the world within seconds. In recent times, this field has witnessed remarkable progress and continues to expand rapidly. Electronic media has brought a revolutionary change to human life. In particular, the widespread availability of mobile phones has made it possible to reach people from all walks of life. Today, the smartphone is not only a tool of communication but, with the help of the internet, has become the most powerful and efficient source for the dissemination of information and news.¹⁶ The media is a powerful means through which the message of truth,

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goodness and reform can be spread. It can be used to promote virtue, knowledge and positive values. Media can serve as an effective tool to awaken public awareness, inspire emotions and guide people toward the right path. When used wisely and responsibly, it can become a source of peace, goodwill and justice in the world. However, advice and guidance should always be delivered with consideration of people's understanding, circumstances and intellectual capacity, so that it touches their hearts and brings about meaningful social change.¹⁷ In the modern era, social media has become the most influential means of social life, but it is also associated with many challenges:

1. **Fake News and Rumors:** Among the biggest challenges of modern social media are fake news and rumors. These often spread rapidly without verification, causing social unrest, hatred and mental stress. The Qur'an has given clear guidance:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا إِن جَاءَكُمْ فَاسِقٌ بِنَبَأٍ فَتَبَيَّنُوا أَن تُصِيبُوا قَوْمًا بِجَهَالَةٍ فَتُصْحَبُوا عَلٰى مَا فَعَلْتُمْ نَادِمِينَ ﴿١٨﴾

Translation: "O you who have believed, if there comes to you a disobedient one with information, investigate, lest you harm a people out of ignorance and become, over what you have done, regretful."

In the light of this verse, it is necessary that both individuals and the state verify information and stop the spread of fake news by enhancing media literacy and public awareness. Research shows that fact-checking institutions and credible news sources play an effective role in preventing rumors. The Holy Prophet ﷺ said:

مِنْ حُسْنِ إِسْلَامِ الْمَرْءِ تَرْكُهُ مَا لَا يَعْنِيهِ-^{١٩}

Translation: "Indeed among the excellence of a person's Islam is that he leaves what does not concern him."

This Hadith teaches that among the best qualities of a believer is that he refrains from matters that do not concern him. This principle guides young people to use digital media thoughtfully and according to needs and purposes, not to waste time on irrelevant or purposeless content and to focus their attention on positive and beneficial activities.

كَفَى بِالْمَرْءِ كَذِبًا أَنْ يُحَدِّثَ بِكُلِّ مَا سَمِعَ-^{٢٠}

Translation: "It is enough of a lie for a man to narrate everything he hears."

This Hadith proves that the truthfulness of information and the accuracy of news are very important and it is necessary for a person not to spread everything he hears without verification. Traditional media have for centuries been the primary means of shaping public opinion and intellectually educating youth. Articles and editorials published in newspapers raise political and social awareness among young people, radio reaches a wider audience through its voice and promotes national unity and television conveys

social values not only through news but also through dramas and other programs. The greatest strength of these media was their research and editorial scrutiny. Since the content was published after investigation and editorial review, young people considered it credible and trustworthy. This is why these media nurtured fundamental elements such as realism, moderation and responsibility in youth.

2. **Moral Decline and Indecency:** Due to the spread of moral decline and indecency on social media, social values and individual character are affected. The younger generation is directly influenced by inappropriate content, obscenity and immoral messages, which weaken confidence, self-respect and social harmony. The Messenger ﷺ said:

"إِذَا لَمْ تَسْتَحْيِ فَافْعَلْ مَا شِئْتَ" ٢١

Translation: If you do not feel ashamed, then do whatever you like.

This Hadith clarifies that modesty is the foundation of morality and without it, every action can be harmful. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the state and educational institutions to promote moral training, modesty and principles of decency among the youth, so that both the individual and society remain protected from the negative impacts of social media. The Western lifestyle is often portrayed as appealing and superior with the underlying aim of promoting immorality, indecency, materialism, dishonesty and neglect of moral and familial values within Muslim societies. Such portrayals attempt to blur the boundaries between halal and haram, weakening the ethical foundation and spiritual consciousness of the Muslim community.²² Through Western movies and television dramas, a favorable image of Western civilization, culture and ideology is deliberately cultivated in the minds of Muslims. This subtle influence leads to the indirect acceptance and implementation of Western policies in Muslim societies. The West continuously strives, by every possible means, to undermine and weaken the position of Muslims in various spheres of life be it intellectual, cultural, or political.²³

3. **Hate Speech and Discord:** Hate speech on social media and messages that promote racial, religious, or sectarian prejudice severely damage social harmony. Such statements not only weaken brotherhood but also increase the chances of mistrust and conflict among individuals. The Messenger ﷺ said:

"لَا تَحَاسَدُوا، وَلَا تَبَاغَضُوا، وَلَا تَقَاطَعُوا، وَكُونُوا عِبَادَ اللَّهِ إِخْوَانًا" ٢٤

Translation: "Nurse no grudge, nurse no aversion and do not sever ties of kinship and live like fellow-brothers as servants of Allah."

This Hadith clarifies that Muslims are brothers to one another and promoting any form of enmity or hatred is forbidden. In this context, it is the responsibility of the state to legally and ethically limit hate speech and prioritize positive and benevolent messages for the promotion of social harmony.

4. **Wastage of Time and Mental Stress:** Modern social media platforms cause a waste of time for both the youth and adults. The continuous flow of news, videos and updates promotes mental stress, anxiety and distraction. The Qur'an states:

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وَالْعَصْرِ ﴿١﴾ إِنَّ الْإِنْسَانَ لِرَبِّهِ لَكُفْرٌ ﴿٢﴾ ٢٥

Translation: "By time, Indeed, mankind is in loss."

These verses highlight the importance of time in human life and the negative effects of its wastage. It is the responsibility of the state and educational institutions to provide training to the youth about valuing time, effective planning and balanced use of social media so that they may avoid stress and the harm of wasted time.

Curriculum and Media Literacy

No concept of social reform can be complete without education and training. In the modern era, where social media and other digital platforms have become part of the daily life of the younger generation, the inclusion of media literacy in the curriculum has become highly essential. It not only provides youth with the training to verify information but also prepares them for responsible communication. The Messenger ﷺ said:

طَلَبُ الْعِلْمِ فَرِيضَةٌ عَلَى كُلِّ مُسْلِمٍ ٢٦

Translation: "Seeking knowledge is a duty upon every Muslim."

This Hadith makes it clear that acquiring knowledge is obligatory upon every Muslim and in today's era this also includes training for the responsible use of media, so that youth may use social media for positive and constructive purposes. It is the responsibility of the state to include such subjects and lessons in the educational curriculum that guide youth towards the positive and responsible use of media. Media ethics are essentially those principles and values through which youth learn how to spread news or information in a correct, impartial and respectful manner. If media ethics are included in the curriculum, students will not only understand truthfulness, honesty and responsibility but also develop the ability to avoid fake news, hatred and negative propaganda. In this way, the state can play an effective role in creating a conscious and responsible citizen society.

The state should ensure the inclusion of the following points in the curriculum:

Media Ethics: Media ethics refers to the principles, regulations and values under which media performs its activities in a transparent, responsible and socially beneficial manner. It includes truthfulness, impartiality, honesty, respect for others, protection of privacy and avoidance of false or misleading information. Media ethics teaches that news and opinion should be kept separate, rumors should be avoided and justice, peace and goodwill should be promoted in society. Its purpose is that media should not be only a source of information but also an effective means of social reform, education and promotion of positive behavior.

Verification of News: Inclusion of training for news verification in the curriculum is extremely necessary so that youth can differentiate between correct and false information. In the era of social media and digital platforms, rumors and fake news spread rapidly. Therefore, students

should be taught to examine the source, timing and credibility of information before believing or sharing it. Verification of news encourages critical thinking, responsibility and caution, resulting in students becoming a shield against misleading information for both themselves and society.

Islamic Communicative Principles: The inclusion of Islamic communicative principles in the curriculum is important because it teaches youth ways of communication based on goodwill, wisdom, truth and justice. In the Seerah of the ﷺ, we find practical examples of how he conveyed messages with gentleness, patience and wisdom, leading to social reform. The Qur'an and Hadith also provide guidance in communication on truthfulness, goodwill and moderation. If students are taught these principles through the curriculum, they will be able to deliver messages not only in their daily conversations but also through social media and modern communication means with responsibility and moral values.

Digital Responsibility: Digital responsibility means that youth should use social media and modern communication platforms in a positive, safe and effective manner. The curriculum should include training that teaches students to use digital platforms for learning, research, communication and positive expression instead of wasting time. Alongside this, youth should also be made aware of the importance of respecting others in online communication, protecting personal information and avoiding false or harmful content. In this way, they can not only build their personality but also prove to be responsible digital citizens at the societal level. Teacher training and awareness programs are also essential so that they may guide youth to use media with awareness and insight.

Legislation and State Policy

The responsibility of the state is not limited to maintaining law and order but also includes social reform, moral training and ensuring welfare. The Qur'an states:

"وَلْتَكُنْ مِنْكُمْ أُمَّةٌ يَدْعُونَ إِلَى الْخَيْرِ وَيَأْمُرُونَ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَيَنْهَوْنَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ ۗ وَأُولَٰئِكَ
سُمُّ الْمُفْلِحُونَ ﴿١٠٢﴾" ٢٧

Translation: "And let there be [arising] from you a nation inviting to [all that is] good, enjoining what is right and forbidding what is wrong and those will be the successful."

This verse highlights three important aspects of the state's responsibility: encouragement of good, prevention of evil and strengthening of social values. In the context of social media today, its practical effects are as follows:

1. **Legal restrictions on fake news and rumors:** The government should implement strict laws to prevent false and harmful content on social media.
2. **Control over hate speech, obscenity and prejudice:** Any speech that harms social harmony must face legal action.

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3. **Support of positive and constructive content:** The state should promote positive and moral messages in educational and entertainment content.
4. **Training in education and public awareness:** Through workshops, seminars and awareness programs, the public and youth should be trained in the responsible use of social media.

Through these measures, not only can social harmony be established, but youth can also be guided to become responsible citizens. This responsibility of the state, within legal and moral boundaries, is essential for social reform and moral training.

Social Awareness and Public Consciousness

Social reform is not possible only through the implementation of laws or policies, but public awareness, training and moral consciousness are also essential. The Holy Qur'an has explained this matter. These teachings make it clear that cooperation for social welfare and refraining from evil are necessary, which are the fundamental principles of social reform.

The Holy Prophet ﷺ also provided guidance regarding public ethics and communication. The teaching of Hadith also conveys the same message—that for the promotion of social harmony and moral values, it is necessary that every individual should speak positively and responsibly, or remain silent.

Summary

Islam is a comprehensive system of life that provides guidance for the individual, society and the state. Truthfulness, trustworthiness, wisdom, goodwill and moderation are the fundamental principles in communication. The responsibility of the state is not only administrative but also moral, religious and educational. Education and training are the foundations of the state and it is essential to promote the positive use of all means of communication, including social media. Through legal, educational and public measures, social reform becomes possible.

Results

1. The Seerah of the ﷺ and Islamic teachings provide clear guidance for the youth to use social media for positive and constructive purposes.
2. The primary responsibility of the state is justice, trust and the welfare of the people.
3. Education, training and media literacy programs help in teaching the youth responsible communication.
4. Without legal and ethical measures, social harmony and moral standards cannot be maintained.
5. Public awareness and sensitization campaigns are essential for social reform.

Recommendations

1. The implementation of justice and fairness should be given top priority.
2. Integrity, ethics and competence should be considered essential qualities in rulers and officials.
3. The curriculum should include moral training, media literacy and Islamic principles of communication.
4. Positive content on social media should be encouraged, while harmful and negative content should be restricted.
5. Workshops and seminars should be organized to raise public awareness and consciousness.
6. Youth should be trained in the positive use of time so that they can avoid stress and time wastage.
7. Effective accountability institutions should be established to ensure ethical and legal responsibilities are fulfilled.
8. The state and educational institutions should work together for social harmony, brotherhood and the reform of society.

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